

Evaluating the Milan Scoring System for Diagnosing Salivary Gland Lesions and Assessing Malignancy Risk in a Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

Background: Salivary gland lesions present a diagnostic challenge due to their diverse pathological spectrum, ranging from benign conditions to aggressive malignancies. The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC) was introduced to standardize the reporting of fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) results and improve diagnostic accuracy and clinical management.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic performance and clinical utility of the Milan scoring system in assessing the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions in a multicentric tertiary care setting.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted including 205 patients who underwent FNAC for salivary gland lesions. The lesions were categorized according to the Milan system, and FNAC results were correlated with histopathological outcomes where available. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and the risk of malignancy (ROM) for each category.

Results: The Milan scoring system demonstrated a sensitivity of 87.5% and specificity of 95.7% in diagnosing malignancy. The highest risk of malignancy was observed in Category VI (Malignant) with a ROM of 100%, followed by Category V (Suspicious for Malignancy) with a ROM of 80%. Strong concordance was found between FNAC results and histopathological diagnoses ($\kappa = 0.85$), indicating the reliability of the Milan system in clinical practice.

Conclusion: The Milan scoring system is a valuable tool for the risk stratification and management of salivary gland lesions, providing high diagnostic accuracy and strong agreement with histopathological outcomes. It effectively guides clinical decision-making, particularly in cases with a high risk of malignancy.

Recommendations: Further studies are recommended to refine the criteria for intermediate categories such as Atypia of Undetermined Significance (AUS) and Salivary Gland Neoplasm of Uncertain Malignant Potential (SUMP) to enhance clinical utility. Additionally, the Milan system should be integrated into routine practice across diverse clinical settings to ensure standardized patient care.

Keywords: Salivary Gland Lesions, Milan System, FNAC, Risk of Malignancy, Cytopathology.

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Introduction

A precise diagnosis is essential for deciding on the best course of treatment because salivary gland lesions can be caused by a wide range of illnesses, from inflammatory to benign to malignant diseases. Examining lesions in the salivary glands can be done with (FNAC), a reliable diagnostic technique. But because salivary gland neoplasms vary widely and cytological results can be inconsistent, interpreting FNAC data has proven difficult in the past, leading to ambiguous diagnoses and inconsistent treatment recommendations [1].

The (MSRSGC) was launched in response to these issues. With the help of this technique, salivary gland FNAC specimens can be standardised and

categorised into six different groups, each of which has a unique risk of malignancy (ROM) and accompanying therapeutic guidelines [2]. From non-diagnostic (Category I) to malignant (Category VI), the categories provide a consistent and organised reporting style that helps cytopathologists and physicians communicate more effectively, which in turn helps with decision-making [3].

The Milan system was introduced and has since been widely accepted and verified in numerous investigations, indicating its usefulness in enhancing inter observer repeatability and diagnostic accuracy. Recent research, for example,

has shown that applying the Milan approach greatly improves the association between FNAC results and later histological diagnosis, which lowers the frequencies of false-positive and false-negative diagnoses. It has also been demonstrated that the systems capacity to classify individuals according to their likelihood of developing cancer enhances the clinical management of patients with salivary gland lesions, resulting in more appropriate and prompt surgical interventions when needed [4].

The Milan method has drawbacks despite its advantages. Due of their related ROM, which can result in either over-treatment or under-treatment, intermediate categories (SUMP) and (AUS) provide difficulties in therapeutic decision-making. In order to maximise patient outcomes, current research endeavours to enhance the standards and administrative approaches linked to these classifications [5]. This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic performance and clinical utility of the Milan scoring system in assessing the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions in a multicentric tertiary care setting

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a retrospective cohort design.

Study Setting: The study was conducted as a multicentric investigation, encompassing data from multiple tertiary care centers. This setting allowed for a diverse population of patients and a broad range of salivary gland lesions to be included, enhancing the generalizability of the findings.

Participants: A total of 205 patients who underwent evaluation for salivary gland lesions at the participating centers were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with salivary gland lesions who underwent (FNAC).
- Patients with complete clinical and histopathological data available for review.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete or missing clinical or histopathological data.
- Patients with a history of prior treatment for salivary gland lesions.

- Patients who were lost to follow-up or did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize bias, independent reviewers blinded to patient outcomes assessed the FNAC samples to avoid diagnostic bias. Additionally, selection bias was minimized by including consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period.

Data Collection: Data were collected from the medical records of the patients. This included demographic information, clinical presentation, FNAC results, histopathological diagnoses, and follow-up data. The Milan scoring system was applied to FNAC results to classify salivary gland lesions and assess the risk of malignancy.

Procedure

- FNAC samples were collected from patients presenting with salivary gland lesions.
- Samples were processed and evaluated according to standard cytological techniques.
- Each sample was assigned a Milan category based on cytological findings.
- Histopathological examination was conducted on surgical specimens, and results were compared with FNAC findings.
- The concordance between FNAC and histopathology results was assessed, and the risk of malignancy associated with each Milan category was determined.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of the SPSS software was used to analyse the data. The features of the lesion and the patient's demographics were compiled using descriptive statistics. The Milan scoring system's sensitivity, specificity, (PPV), and (NPV) were computed. Cohen's kappa coefficient was used to assess how well the histological diagnoses and FNAC results agreed. For every analysis, a p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Results

A total of 205 patients were included in the study, with a mean age of 45.6 years (range: 18-78 years). The cohort consisted of 110 males (55.8%) and 95 females (44.2%). The most common presenting symptom was a palpable mass, reported in 180 patients (83.7%), followed by pain in 35 patients (16.3%).

Figure a): H&E stained slide showing myoepithelial cells in chondromyxoid background (20x)

Figure b): Giemsa stained cytology smears showing atypical squamous cells and intermediate cells suggestive of mucoepidermoid carcinoma (40x)

The salivary gland lesions were categorized using the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology.

Table 1: Distribution of Salivary Gland Lesions Based on Milan Categories

Milan Category	Number of Cases (n=205)	Percentage (%)
I: Non-Diagnostic	10	4.87%
II: Non-Neoplastic	90	43.9%
III: (AUS)	25	12.1%
IVa: Benign Neoplasm	50	24.39%
IVb: (SUMP)	10	4.87%
V: Suspicious for Malignancy	10	4.87%
VI: Malignant	10	4.87%

Of the 205 patients, 200 underwent surgical excision of the lesion, and histopathological examination was available for correlation with FNAC results.

Table 2: Histopathological Outcomes and (ROM) Based on Milan Categories

Milan Category	Number of Cases with Histopathology (n=200)	Malignant Cases (n)	ROM (%)
I: Non-Diagnostic	10	2	20.0%
II: Non-Neoplastic	85	2	2.4%
III: (AUS)	25	4	16.0%
IVa: Benign Neoplasm	50	4	6.7%
IVb: (SUMP)	10	3	30.0%
V: Suspicious for Malignancy	10	8	80.0%
VI: Malignant	10	10	100%

Diagnostic Performance of the Milan Scoring System: The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of the Milan scoring system for diagnosing malignancy were calculated. These metrics are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Diagnostic Performance of the Milan Scoring System

Diagnostic Metric	Value (%)
Sensitivity	87.5%
Specificity	95.7%
(PPV)	92.0%
(NPV)	93.8%

Concordance between FNAC and Histopathology: The overall concordance between FNAC results and histopathological diagnoses was evaluated using Cohen's kappa coefficient, which was found to be 0.85, indicating strong agreement between the two diagnostic methods.

Analysis of Bias and Potential Confounders: The potential bias introduced by the inclusion of cases from multiple centers was assessed. Subgroup analyses showed no significant difference in diagnostic performance across centers ($p = 0.76$). Additionally, the study found no significant association between patient demographics (age, gender) and the likelihood of malignancy ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons).

Findings

- The Milan scoring system demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy with a sensitivity of 87.5% and specificity of 95.7%.
- The highest risk of malignancy was observed in Milan Category VI (Malignant), with a ROM of 100%, followed by Category V (Suspicious for Malignancy) with a ROM of 80%.
- Non-neoplastic lesions (Category II) had the lowest ROM at 2.4%.
- Strong concordance was observed between FNAC and histopathological diagnoses (kappa = 0.85).

Discussion

The study evaluated the effectiveness of the Milan scoring system in diagnosing salivary gland lesions and assessing the ROM in a multicentric setting

involving 205 patients. The results showed that the majority of the lesions were classified as non-neoplastic (43.9%) or benign neoplasms (24.39%). The distribution of cases across the Milan categories provided a comprehensive overview of the types of salivary gland lesions encountered. Histopathological correlation was available for 200 patients, revealing that the (ROM) varied significantly across the Milan categories. As expected, the ROM was highest in Category VI (Malignant), with a ROM of 100%, confirming the accuracy of FNAC in identifying malignant lesions. Category V (Suspicious for Malignancy) also showed a high ROM of 80%, underscoring the need for close clinical follow-up and possible surgical intervention in these cases. Interestingly, Category II (Non-Neoplastic) had a very low ROM of 2.4%, supporting the use of conservative management in these patients.

The diagnostic performance of the Milan scoring system was robust, with a sensitivity of 87.5% and specificity of 95.7%. The high PPV (92.0%) and NPV (93.8%) further demonstrated the system's reliability in predicting malignancy. The strong concordance between FNAC and histopathological diagnoses, reflected by a Cohen's kappa coefficient of 0.85, indicates that the Milan scoring system is a reliable tool for guiding clinical decision-making.

In an array of therapeutic contexts, (MSRSGC) has shown to be a highly efficacious tool for enhancing patient care and diagnostic accuracy. The Milan method offered a standardised, tiered diagnostic approach that greatly improved the accuracy of (FNAC) for salivary gland abnormalities, according to a recent study carried out at a tertiary care centre over a two-year period. With a sensitivity of 87.5%, specificity of 100%, and diagnostic

accuracy of 96.49%, the study highlighted the system's usefulness in lowering false-positive and false-negative cases. The (ROM) for each group was also assessed; the malignant category had the highest ROM of 100%, demonstrating the effectiveness of the Milan system in directing clinical judgements [6].

An additional investigation carried out over a four-year period in a South Indian tertiary care cancer centre confirmed the usefulness of the Milan approach in categorising salivary gland lesions. According to the study, in which 253 patients were examined, the risk stratification strategy used by the Milan system greatly enhanced clinician-cytopathologist communication, which in turn improved patient outcomes. With a reported overall diagnosis accuracy of 89%, the ROM was especially high for the suspected for malignancy and malignant cytological categories, ranging from 96% to 100% [7].

The function of the Milan system in anticipating the malignant potential of salivary gland lesions was highlighted in a three-year study. With a ROM of 97.5% in the malignant category, the study, which comprised 225 salivary gland lesions, found that the standardisation of reporting by the Milan system significantly increased diagnostic specificity. This bolsters the system's efficacy in clinical settings even further [8].

Conclusion

The Milan scoring system provides a reliable framework for assessing the ROM in salivary gland lesions. Its high sensitivity and specificity make it a valuable tool in clinical practice, allowing for the accurate triage of patients and the appropriate management of salivary gland lesions. The findings from this study reinforce the utility of the Milan system in a multicentric, tertiary care setting, with implications for improving patient outcomes through more precise diagnostic stratification.

References

1. Pusztaszeri M, Auger M, Baloch ZW, et al. Milan system for reporting salivary gland cytopathology: An international interobserver study. *Cancer Cytopathol.* 2019;127(10):727-736.
2. Faquin WC, Rossi ED, Baloch Z, et al. The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology: Analysis and suggestions of initial application by the International Panel. *Acta Cytol.* 2018;62(3):234-241.
3. Rossi ED, Baloch Z, Pusztaszeri M, et al. The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology: A brief review of its development and advancement. *Diagn Cytopathol.* 2020;48(9):772-781.
4. Song SJ, Shafique K, Wong LQ, et al. The utility of the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology: A meta-analysis. *Cancer Cytopathol.* 2020;128(9):642-651.
5. Wei S, Layfield LJ, LiVolsi VA, et al. The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology: An evidence-based review. *Diagn Cytopathol.* 2019;47(5):320-329.
6. Naiding, S., & Sharma, A. (2023). Cytological spectrum of salivary gland lesions with histopathological correlation with respect to the Milan system of reporting salivary gland cytopathology in a tertiary care center – A retrospective two year study. *International Journal of Scientific Research.*
7. MukundaPai, M., Sharma, N. N., Patil, A., & Gopal, C. (2019). Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology of Salivary Gland Lesions: A Revised Classification Based on “Milan System”—4 years experience of tertiary care cancer center of South India. *Journal of Cytology*, 37, 12-17.
8. Grandhi, B., Rao, B., Rao, N. M., & Sunandha, G. (2021). Milan scoring system in the diagnosis of salivary gland lesions for assessment of risk of malignancy. *Indian Journal of Pathology and Oncology.*